

Studies on N-Substituted Salicylhydroxamic Acid as Metal-Complexing Ligand : Part IV. U(VI)-Complexes of N-Phenyl Salicylhydroxamic Acid

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N-phenyl salicylhydroxamic acid (RH_2) forms a number of coloured complexes with U(VI) in 1 : 1 aqueous ethanol at different pH values. So it is worthwhile to study the compositions of such compounds by Job's method of continued variation¹.

EXPERIMENTAL

All the solutions were made in 1 : 1 aqueous ethanol, water used was double distilled and ethanol of Spek-pure quality. Other reagents were properly purified. Optical densities

1. P. Job, *Ann. Chim.*, 1928, 9, (10) 113.

of the solutions were measured with a spectrophotometer (Hilger) using 1 cm quartz cell against water as blank. Uranyl nitrate hexahydrate A.R. (5.589 g) was dissolved in 250 ml. of 0.05N HNO_3 and was standardised by estimating uranium gravimetrically as U_3O_8 . The U(VI) solutions of required strengths were then prepared from the above stock solution.

A : Spectral curves : Before studying the formation of complexes by Job's method, spectral curves were drawn for each complex formed at three different pH values. For this purpose three sets of solutions were prepared at three different pH values ≈ 2.0 , ≈ 4.5 and $\approx 5.8-6.0$ where 3 ml of U(VI) solution in each case were mixed with 3 ml, 6 ml and 9 ml equimolecular solution of RH_2 in three 25 ml volumetric flasks and after adjusting pH with standard HCl or NaOH or with sodium acetate-acetic acid buffer, the volume was made upto the mark with 1 : 1 aqueous ethanol. Optical densities were measured at different wave lengths against water as blank. Results are stated graphically by plotting optical densities against the corresponding wave lengths (Fig. 1). From the spectral curves 480 $m\mu$ and 450 $m\mu$ were chosen to study the U(VI) complexes by Job's method at three different pH values ≈ 2.0 , ≈ 4.5 and $\approx 5.8-6.0$.

B : Job's method : Equimolecular solutions of U(VI) and RH_2 in 1 : 1 aqueous ethanol were mixed in different ratios in a number of 25 ml volumetric flasks. pH of the mixtures

were adjusted with standard HCl/NaOH or with sodium acetate-acetic acid buffer and the volume was made upto the mark in each case. Optical densities were measured against water at two different wave lengths $480\text{ m}\mu$ and $450\text{ m}\mu$ at each pH value ≈ 2.0 or ≈ 4.5 or $\approx 5.8-6.0$. Results are stated graphically in Figs. 2 and 3.

FIG. 3

DISCUSSION

From the data it is evident that N-phenyl salicylhydroxamic acid (RH_2) forms two different coloured complexes (reddish brown and yellow) with U(VI) both having the same composition i.e. $U : RH_2 = 1 : 1$ at lower and higher pH values ≈ 2.0 and 6.0 respectively. At intermediate pH values $\approx 2.7-4.5$ another complex has been detected with the composition $U : RH_2 = 2 : 3$, the colour being orange-brown. The bis-chelate of U(VI) with N-methyl salicylhydroxamic acid² has been isolated in the solid state but in case of N-phenyl salicylhydroxamic acid the compound isolated³ in the solid state has the composition $U : RH_2 = 1 : 1$ and $1 : 2$. Diuranates ($M_2U_2O_7$) are formed at pH near about 6. So the $1 : 1$ compound at higher pH may be assumed to have a diuranate-like structure.

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Received November 6, 1969

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